

SHORT NOTES

ATOMIC AND STRUCTURAL RHEOCHORS

BY R. P. SHUKLA

Rheochor can be as useful as parachor in predicting the structures of organic compounds. It can also be used for finding the viscosities of liquids (Shukla and Bhatnagar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 988). But because of the lack of consolidated data on the atomic and structural rheochors, it has not been possible to use it. Bhagwat, Toshniwal and Moghe (this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 30) have used the equation $M\eta^{\frac{1}{3}}/d$ for finding the rheochor of substances, while Subnis, Bhagwat and Silawat (*ibid.*, 1946, 26, 534) have used the equation $M(\eta \times 10^3)^{\frac{1}{3}}/d$, and hence, according to Bhagwat *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) the value for methyl alcohol is 21.33, while Subnis *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have suggested the value 50.3. The present work has been undertaken to co-ordinate the results of the two workers and to have consolidated data on rheochor. The results obtained in the present investigation are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

[M, d , and R have usual the significance. All the viscosities are in centipoises and we have used the formula suggested by Newton Friend, *Nature*, 1942, 148, 432].

No.	Substance	'M'	'd'	$\eta \times 100$	'R'
1.	Ethyl ether	74.12	0.7146	0.25	49.00
2.	<i>iso</i> Propyl ether	102.17	0.7244	0.34	69.33
3.	Butyl ether	130.22	0.7694	0.69	90.84
4.	Acetone	56.08	0.7910	0.35	36.21
5.	Methyl <i>isobutyl</i> ketone	100.16	0.8042	0.59	65.46
6.	Methyl amyl ketone	114.18	0.8166	0.65	74.35
7.	Benzene	78.00	0.8646	0.57	47.29
8.	Butylamine	73.14	0.7385	0.50	80.95
9.	Mercaptoethanol	78.13	1.1198	3.43	45.76
10.	Trichloroethane	133.42	1.4432	1.20	53.19

All the values are at 20°.

The difference for CH_2 has been calculated from sets of values shown below.

TABLE II

S. No.	System	Value for CH_2 .
2-1	<i>iso</i> Propyl ether—ethyl ether	2 (10.14)
3-1	Butyl ether—ethyl ether	4 (10.45)
3-2	Butyl ether— <i>isopropyl</i> ether	2 (10.75)
6-5	Methyl <i>isobutyl</i> ketone—acetone	3 (9.75)
7-5	Methyl amyl ketone—acetone	4 (9.53)
7-6	Methyl amyl ketone—methyl <i>isobutyl</i> ketone	(8.86)
	Average	9.91

In the present work all the non-associated liquids have been taken and the value determined. As will be seen, it comes to be 9.91. Substituting this value in *n*-hexane one obtains the value for H atom as 2.06 and C as 5.89.

While from ether the value for O comes to be 5.34. Similarly by substituting the values in different compounds, the following results have been obtained.

TABLE III

S. No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Atom	H	C	O	Cl	S	N	Double bond	Six—membered ring
Value	2.01	5.98	5.34	11.79	23.84	35.28	1.14	—3.73

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DETECTION OF COBALT BY *o*-PHENYLENEDIAMINE

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o-Phenylenediamine has earlier been proposed as a reagent for the detection of nickel and vanadium. Nickel yields in presence of ammonia a bluish purple precipitate (Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. II, p. 430; Feigl, *Oestr. Chem. Ztg.*, 1923, 28, 85; 1927, 30, 13; *Monatsh.*, 1927, 48, 445). But the test does not respond in dilute solutions, as the complex under these conditions is wholly dissociated into its constituents (Heiber *et al.*, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1929, 180, 89). *o*-Phenylenediamine hydrochloride develops an orange-yellow colour with a vanadate (Rosenthaler, *Mikrochem.*, 1937, 23, 194), but the test is not a sensitive one for vanadium. It has been observed that interaction of *o*-phenylenediamine with cobalt and dimethylglyoxime produces an intense unstable colour (Lee and Diehl, *Proc. Iowa Acad. Sci.*, 1950, 57, 187; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, 7911) but no study of the interaction of cobalt and *o*-phenylenediamine, with particular reference to its applicability as a means of detecting cobalt, has been made. It has now been observed that *o*-phenylenediamine alone gives rise to an intense violet coloration with traces of cobalt in alkaline medium.

Qualitative detection of cobalt was carried out in aqueous medium. In aqueous medium the development of the violet colour is not immediate but requires a little time and shaking. Calcium, strontium, barium, magnesium, zinc, cadmium, lead, beryllium, aluminium, thallium, uranium, thorium, zirconium, titanium and bismuth do not interfere. Manganese interferes due to precipitation of higher manganese oxides in the alkaline medium. Ferric iron, silver, mercuric mercury etc. immediately oxidise the